

Exploring ChatGPT to Assist English Language Learners' Learning Process

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ABSTRACT

The current study investigates the utilization of ChatGPT to assist students in their language learning process through a descriptive qualitative study. Research data was collected via semi-structured interviews using purposive sampling, targeting five English language education students at a private faith-based university in Purwokerto. The findings indicate that students understand the use of ChatGPT and can effectively use prompts to interact with it. The study also indicates that participants generally use ChatGPT to assist with completing assignments, language learning, and writing their final projects. Participants commonly found that ChatGPT provided inaccurate information and lacked contextual understanding. To address these challenges, they cross-referenced information from ChatGPT with their own knowledge and reliable sources. The study also identified potential challenges such as plagiarism, using ChatGPT for cheating, and dependency on ChatGPT to complete assignments. This study supports the notion that ChatGPT can facilitate and support the language learning process for students.

1. Introduction

Technological developments have reached the stage of creating Artificial Intelligence (Henceforth abbreviated as AI). AI has been widely used to facilitate human activities in various fields. In the field of education, especially language learning, AI has been used to support learning activities. For instance, AI can suggest suitable learning materials, identify areas needing improvement, and modify the difficulty level of tasks (Harry, 2023). One AI that is widely used in language learning is ChatGPT. ChatGPT was created by OpenAI on November 30, 2022. ChatGPT is an AI-based chatbot that is programmed to answer commands or requests given by users. ChatGPT facilitates language learning by imitating real-world conversations (Kohnke et al., 2023).

ChatGPT can provide easy access to large amounts of information from various sources such as books, articles, journals or other information sources and provide fast responses to users, this can make ChatGPT as a quasi-virtual library that can help people who need information quickly and cannot go to the physical library (Aithal & Aithal, 2023). The ease and sophistication of using ChatGPT makes many students use ChatGPT as an aid in their

learning process, especially in learning English. According to a study conducted by Maulana et al., the reason many students use ChatGPT is because they can do assignments, essays, papers and scientific papers easily and quickly by using the right prompt technique (Maulana et al., 2023). Although ChatGPT has advantage, the researcher are aware that ChatGPT also has limitations. This AI can provide misinformation as clearly as providing actual facts is one of the shortcomings of ChatGPT (Thirunavukarasu et al., 2023). However, ChatGPT still has the potential to help English language learning.

The current study at least fills three gaps from previous study. First, the participants in this study were English language education students from a private, faith-based university. In previous study, they used participants from universities (Xiao & Zhi, 2023; Shoufan, 2023) and secondary public schools (Javier & Moorhouse, 2023). Second, current study focuses on the extent to which ChatGPT helps students in their learning process. On the other hand, previous study focuses on the potential and challenges of ChatGPT (Shoufan, 2023), how to develop the use of ChatGPT among secondary English language learners (Javier & Moorhouse, 2023), and the extent to which ChatGPT helps students to complete language learning assignments (Xiao & Zhi, 2023). Lastly, their study used indicators from a particular theoretical review (Javier & Moorhouse, 2023; Shoufan, 2023; Xiao & Zhi, 2023), while this study used indicators created by Xiao & Zhi (2023).

From the explanation above, the aim of this research is to find out how well students understand using ChatGPT, explore how students use ChatGPT in their learning process, and investigate the challenges students face in using ChatGPT. To fulfill the objectives, this study has research question: "To what extent do students use ChatGPT to assist their English learning process?"

2. Literature Review

2.1 AI-Powered Chatbot

In education, technological developments play an important role. In this technological development, there are traditional digital language learning technologies (TDLLT) and emerging language learning technologies (ELLT). Traditional digital language learning technologies (TDLLT) refer to computer and software programs specifically designed for language learning through various digital platforms, including desktop applications, online websites, and mobile apps (Shaikh et al., 2023). This technology can increase the effectiveness of language learning at certain level and is already widely used (Chun et al., 2023). In recent developments, emerging language learning technologies (ELLT), which leverage advanced techniques such as virtual reality (VR), artificial intelligence (AI), natural language processing (NLP), and gamification, represent the latest innovations designed to enhance the language learning experience (Shaikh et al., 2023). These technologies are more advanced and have a significant and measurable impact on facilitating more effective English language learning (Klimova et al., 2023).

Recently, chatbot and conversational AI are already widely used in education. A chatbot is an application that utilizes language models and algorithms to mimic informal conversations with users via natural language, and it is extensively applied in education, business, healthcare, and other domains of life (Ashfaque et al., 2020). By utilizing natural language processing (NLP) and machine learning methods, chatbots can adjust to learners'

proficiency levels and tailor the learning content (Xiao & Zhi, 2023). Chatbots serve three functions in education: acting as teaching assistants, learning partners, and personal tutors (Deng & Yu, 2023). Harry (2023) also stated that one of the main advantages of utilizing chatbots in education is their capability to offer personalized assistance to students. For example, Annamalai et al. (2023) found that chatbots boost English language learners' competence, autonomy, and relatedness, underscoring the value of providing a supportive, non-judgmental environment for practice, which in turn increases learners' confidence, proficiency, and engagement in the learning process. The current research focuses on ChatGPT, which is one of the chatbots that is currently being widely used by students. The reason many students use ChatGPT is because they can do assignments, essays, papers and scientific papers easily and quickly by using the right prompt technique (Muhammad et al., 2023).

2.2 ChatGPT as an AI-Based Language Learning Assistant

ChatGPT (Generative Pre-trained Transformer) is a language model developed by OpenAI to be able to create text that is similar to human written language by using artificial intelligence (Atlas, 2023). ChatGPT has undergone iterative development from GPT-1 in June 2018 to GPT-4 which was launched in March 2023 (Wu et al., 2023). According to OpenAI (2022), they trained a model called ChatGPT using Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback (RLHF) so that it can interact conversationally and ChatGPT is also trained to be able to follow instructions quickly and provide responses to questions or commands in the form of answers, challenge incorrect premises and reject inappropriate requests from user. ChatGPT can produce more precise replies than manual conversations due to its extensive training on a vast collection of dialogues, enabling it to comprehend the context and generate fitting responses (Deng & Lin, 2022).

ChatGPT has the potential to provide numerous advantages and possibilities for the user. ChatGPT can provide easy access to large amounts of information from various sources such as books, articles, journals or other information sources and provide fast responses to users, this can make ChatGPT as a quasi-virtual library that can help people who need information quickly and cannot go to the physical library (Aithal & Aithal, 2023). ChatGPT also can improve the quality of work in writing and be a valuable resource in higher education because it can generate text, and summarize information and outlines to save time (Halaweh, 2023). According to Zhai (2023) in his piloting study regarding the experience of ChatGPT users, compared to humans, text written by AI has more efficient information, besides that the text written also looks professional, coherent and relatively accurate. In addition to creating texts in a variety of genres, creating quizzes, annotating texts, and providing dictionary definitions, example sentences, and translations, ChatGPT can also recognize the meaning of a word in context and correct and explain language errors (Kohnke et al., 2023).

Despite its benefits, ChatGPT also has several drawbacks. According to (Gilson et al., 2023; Shoufan, 2023) ChatGPT does not scan for up-to-date sources of information needed on the internet because it has limited knowledge until the last time it was updated by OpenAI. Thirunavukarasu et al. (2023) also stated that ChatGPT's ability to provide new information is not always accurate and can even provide inaccurate information as clear as correct facts. Furthermore, according to Kohnke et al. (2023), language learners may not be aware that

ChatGPT is an AI that is not culturally neutral and may even introduce bias because the responses it provides are primarily written rather than spoken. ChatGPT's ability to help students with difficulties easily and quickly through appropriate prompts (Maulana et al., 2023), has the possibility of being used for cheating among students as well. Anders (2023) informed many professors and others in academia about ChatGPT, and most immediately expressed concerns that students might use it for cheating, emphasizing that any form of academic dishonesty, including misrepresenting another person's work as their own, is prohibited and results in an unfair advantage for the cheater or an unfair benefit or disadvantage for other students. On the other hand, the outputs produced by ChatGPT are rephrased versions of its sources without appropriate citations, potentially causing problems like plagiarism (Xiao & Zhi, 2023).

Even though ChatGPT has several shortcomings, this AI still has the potential to be used in English language learning. ChatGPT has the potential to offer a variety of benefits and opportunities for language learning to learners at various proficiency levels (Xiao & Zhi, 2023). ChatGPT is also a large language model that can be used to help all levels of education. Despite the fact that each person has distinct learning preferences, abilities, and needs, large language models offer special opportunities for personalized and effective learning experiences, and can improve learning and teaching experiences for individuals at all levels of education (Kasneji et al., 2023). According to Hong (2023), ChatGPT can be a personal language teacher in learning because it provides many sources and learning materials, explains and gives detailed examples of vocabulary usage, and can quickly provide feedback on the quality of writing.

Shaikh et al. (2023) conducted a study evaluating the usability of ChatGPT for formal English language learning. The study's findings, based on participants' responses to the Usefulness, Satisfaction, and Ease of Use (USE) and System Usability Scale (SUS) questionnaires, offer valuable insights into ChatGPT's usability for this purpose. The positive perceptions regarding usefulness, ease of use, learning facilitation, and satisfaction indicate that ChatGPT holds promising and practical implications for language learners. Additionally, taking user feedback into account, such as interface quality and response accuracy, and incorporating these into further development and improvements of ChatGPT can significantly enhance its overall usability for English language learners.

Xiao & Zhi (2023) embarked on an exploratory study to explore how students experience and perceive ChatGPT in the context of language learning through a qualitative, small-scale investigation. Their findings revealed that students view ChatGPT as a useful learning companion, aiding them in language-related tasks. Participants also showed an ability to critically evaluate the quality of ChatGPT's outputs and adapt prompts to optimize learning, thus addressing potential academic integrity issues. This study provides empirical evidence from the students' perspective, demonstrating ChatGPT's potential in language education. It supports the idea that ChatGPT can offer effective immediate feedback and personalized learning experiences.

According to Farrokhnia et al. (2023), a SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) analysis was conducted for ChatGPT in the context of education. The SWOT analysis reveals that, in addition to numerous strengths and opportunities, ChatGPT also

possesses weaknesses and threats that require attention. The table below summarizes the results of Farrokhnia et al.'s (2023) SWOT analysis of ChatGPT in education:

Table 1: SWOT Analysis of ChatGPT

	Helpful To Achieve Goal	Harmful to Achieve Goal
Internal Factors	Strengths	Weaknesses
	Generating plausible responses	Lack of deep understanding
	Self-improving capability	Difficulty in evaluating the quality of responses
	Providing personalized responses	The risk of biases and discrimination
	Providing real-time responses	Lack of higher-order thinking skills
External Factors	Opportunities	Threats
	Increasing accessibility of information	Lack of understanding the context
	Facilitating personalized learning	Threatening academic integrity
	Facilitating complex learning	Perpetuating discrimination in education
	Decreasing teaching workload	Democratization of plagiarism in education
		Declining in high-order cognitive skills

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Participants / Subject / Population and Sample

In this study, researcher used a descriptive qualitative research design. The characteristic of descriptive qualitative research means that the research attempts to create a systematic, accurate, and factual general description of the facts, characteristics, and relationships between the phenomena being researched (Furidha, 2023). Descriptive qualitative research methods are utilized to thoroughly and accurately depict social reality and various societal phenomena, allowing for a detailed presentation and comprehensive understanding of the traits, nature, and model of the research object (Furidha, 2023). These methods can provided an in-depth picture of the experience of someone interacting with the object being studied. The researcher wanted to explore students' experiences regarding the widespread use of ChatGPT, especially among English Language Learners.

This study involved five English Language Education students from a private university in Purwokerto. The researcher used a purposive sampling technique targeting students who frequently and proficiently had used ChatGPT for 6 months or more to help their English learning process. Students who met the criteria desired by the researcher were categorized as possible participants and were selected as many as the researcher needed in this study.

3.2 Instruments

The researcher used semi-structured interview as a data collection technique. From interviews, researcher could easily get an in-depth explanation regarding student experiences regarding the widespread use of ChatGPT, especially among English Language Learners. The researcher used interview questions based on a interview guide proposed by Xiao & Zhi (2023). Several points that were used by researcher in the interviews included knowledge and comprehension of ChatGPT, utilization of ChatGPT in language learning process, and challenge in using ChatGPT. Interviews were conducted using Indonesian as the participant's mother tongue. The interview process was recorded with the consent of the participant.

3.3 Data Analysis Procedures

This study used Miles & Huberman model data analysis. As stated by Creswell (2012), qualitative research data analysis involves preparing and organizing the data, such as text from transcripts or images from photographs, for analysis. Sugiyono (2015) states that the Miles & Huberman model of data analysis involves several steps, including data reduction, data display, and drawing or verifying conclusions. The data will be categorized into several points (knowledge and comprehension of ChatGPT, utilization of ChatGPT in language learning process, and challenge in using ChatGPT).

4. Findings

In the research findings are several simplified participant answers related to understanding the use of ChatGPT, using ChatGPT and also the challenges faced by participants when using ChatGPT to help their learning process. Participants' names were disguised and replaced using aliases (P1, P2, P3, P4, and P5)

4.1 Knowledge and Comprehension of ChatGPT

All participants comprehend the use of ChatGPT, an AI chatbot designed for retrieving desired information through dialogues wherein the user provides commands, questions, or inputs, and the chatbot delivers responses, statements, or outputs. Regarding the utilization of ChatGPT, all participants expressed that it is easy to use and that understanding its operation does not require assistance from others; they can learn and explore independently. Participant's answers are as follows:

"The use of ChatGPT is, in my opinion, quite easy because we can simply ask directly what we want to inquire about or what information we want to explore, and ChatGPT responds with many answers sourced from various places... I believe we can understand how to use ChatGPT by self-learning, meaning we do not need to heavily rely on others to help us use or learn how to use ChatGPT." (P1)

"In my opinion, using ChatGPT is easy, not difficult. It is easy to use for those who are new to ChatGPT, and the instructions for use are easy to follow." (P2)

"I am somewhat aware of the common features used, which are usually utilized by university or high school students, such as searching for answers and materials... In my opinion, ChatGPT is user-friendly, as long as we know the context of what we want to ask or what we are looking for, ChatGPT will provide the answers... it seems we do not need help from others... in my opinion, it is easy to use without needing to ask others, the features can be learned on your own." (P3)

"In my opinion, using ChatGPT is very easy. We just open our device or laptop, go to the ChatGPT page, and type the information we want to find... learning how to use ChatGPT can be done personally without needing help from others... we can learn and explore it on our own." (P4)

"Using ChatGPT is quite easy; we just need to use certain prompts to instruct ChatGPT... understanding how to use ChatGPT is actually quite easy... we can explore it on our own... the more we use it, the more creative we become and get used to using prompts for ChatGPT." (P5)

The effective use of prompts by all participants to interact with ChatGPT follows a similar approach. Participants use effective prompts based on specific and clear questions, commands, instructions, or inputs. Providing clear keywords can also maximize the effectiveness of the prompts used, enabling ChatGPT to deliver the desired responses, statements, or outputs. Participant's answers are as follows:

"I often write quite complex commands, listing all the information I want to explore, so ChatGPT responds with all the information I want to get... I often include quotation marks around the points I want to explore." (P1)

"I need to use clear language or clear questions so that ChatGPT understands my questions and gives me the answers I want." (P2)

"I usually use keywords... the language must be clear and easy for the bot to understand... even if we make a typo, ChatGPT still responds, but the answer might be less organized due to incorrect input. However, if we use correct language and keywords, ChatGPT responds with good, complete, and detailed language." (P3)

"We need to type clearly... the command must be clear so that ChatGPT at least provides answers close to what we want, typed according to the needs." (P4)

"The prompt instructions must be specified clearly for ChatGPT to assist us more effectively and precisely... the clearer the prompt instructions, the clearer ChatGPT will provide the needed information." (P5)

4.2 Utilization of ChatGPT in Language Learning Process

4.2.1 Specific Skills Enchanted by ChatGPT

According to all participants, the specific language skill most supported by ChatGPT is writing. However, some participants also noted that ChatGPT supports other language skills such as reading, listening, and speaking. Participant's answers are as follows:

"...the language skills that GPT is highly specialized in, in my opinion, are grammar skills, reading, and writing... ChatGPT in English language learning covers all aspects... ChatGPT significantly contributes to important aspects like listening and speaking skills... although it does not help 100%... we can unconsciously learn them." (P1)

"...because I personally use ChatGPT more often for writing skills, ChatGPT is effective in supporting writing skills..." (P2)

"The most supported language skills are writing and reading..." (P3)

"...in my opinion, it leans more towards writing. ChatGPT as a writing assistant is more suitable... although ChatGPT can be used for brainstorming during speaking... in my opinion, ChatGPT is more comfortable and fitting when used as a writing assistant..." (P4)

"Writing... in writing, sometimes grammar or structure layout, ChatGPT helps a lot by correcting them..." (P5)

4.2.2 General Uses of ChatGPT

Although participants generally believe ChatGPT is more geared towards supporting writing skills, it still aids significantly in various aspects of their language learning process. Despite its diverse usage, participants typically use ChatGPT to help with assignments, enhance their language learning, and assist with their final projects. Participant's answers are as follows:

"...I use ChatGPT when doing my college assignments, and I often use ChatGPT to explore information outside of my coursework that I want to delve into... I use ChatGPT as a learning tool." (P1)

"I use ChatGPT to do assignments or to find information when the assignments I am working on are too difficult or require more specific answers." (P2)

"...usually for studying, finding materials, finding answers... in doing assignments..." (P3)

"I use it for various activities... including assignments and practicing my English... using ChatGPT, and even now, during my thesis, I need ChatGPT." (P4)

"I typically use ChatGPT to find ideas or writing references when I hit a roadblock, for instance, in research... ChatGPT also helps me with certain course assignments... indirectly, ChatGPT helps me find information related to my courses." (P5)

4.2.2.1 ChatGPT as a Language Learning Tool

ChatGPT significantly aids participants in their language learning process. The usage of ChatGPT in language learning by participants varies according to their individual needs. Participants adjust their use of ChatGPT to fit their specific language learning requirements. Participant's answers are as follows:

"...For language learning, perhaps I can take an example when I was studying a linguistic structure in the structure course, advanced structure... I used ChatGPT to provide additional information and examples so I could grasp the material correctly... ChatGPT significantly contributed to my activities in writing essays, particularly in developing points, and also for feedback on my writing or development." (P1)

"...When I needed information that I couldn't find on Google, I searched for it on ChatGPT... I often use ChatGPT to summarize or condense some sentences that I think are too long and hard to understand.... providing maybe some example sentences that I need for writing essays... including ideas and concepts,.... looking for information when the assignment I'm working on is too difficult or requires a more specific answer.... for translating some sentences or paragraphs that are difficult." (P2)

"...I asked ChatGPT for help to complement or develop my language skills... Later, I ask ChatGPT to correct my answers... I search for materials to study on my own outside of college assignments... I ask ChatGPT to help write essays... I ask ChatGPT to explain the meaning of questions... ChatGPT helps me correct my grammar and improve my writing style... ChatGPT can assist us by directly translating into Indonesian..." (P3)

"...I use ChatGPT to find additional information related to courses, lessons, material being taught by the lecturer in class... I have used it to find additional information... I use ChatGPT regarding grammar structures that I still don't understand." (P4)

"ChatGPT also helps me with certain course assignments, for instance, it can be used for the structure course... ChatGPT explains... what is being asked in this question, the incomplete sentence, the formula is like this... indirectly, ChatGPT helps me find information related to that course... I use ChatGPT to provide feedback on my work, what needs to be corrected, what is still inaccurate... ChatGPT actually helps me understand the language in ChatGPT... the structure course helps... I have used ChatGPT but only as a reference for writing essays so I know the correct patterns." (P5)

4.2.2.2 ChatGPT for Final Project

According to several participants, they also utilize ChatGPT to assist with their final projects. The final projects, specifically research articles, can benefit from the support provided by ChatGPT. Participant's answers are as follows:

"...Currently, during my thesis period, I find ChatGPT useful for acquiring understanding on information that I am not yet familiar with... It helps clarify aspects such as methodology... ChatGPT can provide an overview... It aids in mapping out potential indicators or variables that may emerge or be discussed." (P4)

"I typically use ChatGPT to seek ideas or writing references when I encounter writer's block, for instance, in research... I look for guidance on how to effectively structure body paragraphs using ChatGPT... It is extremely helpful for drafting essays or research papers... ChatGPT offers references for essay paragraphs, and I also obtain references from previous journals... This assists me in the writing and typing process." (P5)

4.3 Facilitation of Independent Learning

With the convenience and effectiveness offered by ChatGPT, it can facilitate participants' self-directed learning. Participants believe that ChatGPT supports their independent learning efforts. Participant's answers are as follows:

"...Due to its effectiveness, it makes our self-directed learning process easier compared to the methods I previously employed." (P1)

"...ChatGPT... can provide clearer or more detailed information, which helps me learn independently... as we can seek information... and get answers immediately... anytime, anywhere, it's flexible." (P₂)

"...Flexible... it simplifies our learning... can be used anywhere, anytime—whether it's midnight, morning, or afternoon, whenever we need it, it is accessible." (P₃)

"...ChatGPT... with its effectiveness and easy availability, being simple and accessible as long as one has data and a device, facilitates self-directed learning, including for my personal understanding of the necessary material." (P₄)

"Yes, it can facilitate my independent learning." (P₅)

4.5 Challenge in Using ChatGPT

Although ChatGPT offers various conveniences to its users, participants do not always use it seamlessly. They encounter challenges while using ChatGPT and have developed strategies to address these difficulties. Participant's answers are as follows:

"...Sometimes I experience poor signal strength, which prevents ChatGPT from generating responses smoothly. Even when I receive a response that is less than satisfactory, and I provide additional instructions to obtain a different type of response, ChatGPT might still produce the same response as before, leading to an inability to acquire the desired information. This issue is relatively rare but has occurred. When ChatGPT's performance fails to cover my questions, I often exit the platform and seek information manually through Google, Scholar, or articles, performing double cross-checks with knowledge from other sources outside of ChatGPT." He added, "Regarding reference provision, when I ask ChatGPT for information and request that it include references or citations, sometimes the references or citations provided are not accessible manually, such as sources or journal references. When I attempt to access these journals, they might not be available or findable." (P₁)

"...ChatGPT requires an internet connection; it cannot be accessed without one...providing inaccurate information or answers that...feel too robotic. There may be errors in responding to my questions, necessitating that I rephrase my questions, perhaps using simpler or clearer language... ChatGPT sometimes provides inaccurate answers... Personally, I first assess the accuracy of the answers logically, and then I compare them with answers from other sources." (P₂)

"...ChatGPT is a bot, so its language is stiff and formal, which is rarely found in the educational world...There is a limit to the number of sentences or words, so if the text exceeds this limit, it is automatically truncated... The account may easily log out, which can be problematic when quick access is needed... Sometimes, ChatGPT's responses are less accurate, requiring multiple attempts to get the desired answers, even with a good internet connection. Occasionally, ChatGPT will admit to not knowing the answer and apologize for its lack of understanding...When I ask something from ChatGPT, I usually have an idea of what I expect the answer to be. I compare ChatGPT's responses with those from Google and other platforms." (P₃)

"...Network issues... Information provided might be less valid or too general... Responses can be repetitive, and sometimes the answers are simply rephrased versions of previous ones. Comparing this information with articles or journals requires careful examination to ensure it matches what is being sought." (P4)

"...ChatGPT sometimes provides inaccurate information if the prompt is not specific enough. I always cross-check the information with other reliable sources... Sometimes, I rely on my own logical reasoning. If I specify the prompt more precisely, ChatGPT will give more accurate information." (P5)

Participants also recognize potential challenges related to academic integrity that arise with ChatGPT. Participant's answers are as follows:

"...Misuse of ChatGPT, such as simply copy-pasting responses, can lead to issues. Regarding plagiarism, it is primarily the replication of ChatGPT's responses that becomes problematic, not the original sources, as ChatGPT paraphrases these sources. Therefore, plagiarism occurs when students replicate ChatGPT's responses rather than the original sources. Over-reliance on ChatGPT negatively impacts students' development quality." (P1)

"Certainly, there are potential challenges related to academic integrity or ethical issues such as plagiarism or over-dependence on technology... While ChatGPT can provide information not found in other sources, this also creates a high potential for cheating." (P2)

"...Paraphrasing by merely copy-pasting constitutes plagiarism. If students do not engage critically and merely gather answers, ChatGPT can become a tool for cheating among students and users." (P3)

"...The risk of plagiarism is significant if one frequently uses ChatGPT and relies solely on copy-pasting. This can be a potential challenge, as using ChatGPT in various contexts like exams or assignments and relying solely on it is problematic." (P4)

"...Copy-pasting directly from ChatGPT violates ethical standards and constitutes plagiarism... It facilitates cheating... Over-dependence on technology is detrimental." (P5)

5. Discussion

5.1 Knowledge and Comprehension of ChatGPT

Based on the interview results, all participants demonstrated an understanding of ChatGPT, which is an AI chatbot utilized for retrieving desired information through a conversational interface. In this interaction, users provide commands, questions, or inputs, while the chatbot responds with answers, statements, or outputs. All participants agreed that using ChatGPT is straightforward, and they felt capable of learning and exploring its functionalities independently, without the need for external assistance. Furthermore, the effective use of prompts employed by all participants for interacting with ChatGPT followed a similar approach. Participants utilized effective prompts that were based on specific and clear questions, commands, instructions, or inputs. Providing clear keywords can also enhance the effectiveness of the prompts used, enabling ChatGPT to deliver the desired answers, statements, or outputs. This aligns with the study conducted by Maulana et al., which states that many students use ChatGPT because it allows them to complete assignments, essays, research papers, and scientific articles easily and swiftly by employing the appropriate prompting techniques (Maulana et al., 2023).

5.2 Utilization of ChatGPT in Language Learning Process

According to the perspectives of all participants, the specific language skill supported by ChatGPT is writing. This assertion is corroborated by Zhai (2023) in his pilot study on the experiences of ChatGPT users, which indicates that text generated by AI is more efficient in conveying information compared to that produced by humans. Additionally, AI-generated text is often perceived as professional, coherent, and relatively accurate. However, some participants noted that ChatGPT also facilitates other language skills such as reading, listening, and speaking. Despite the emphasis on writing, participants acknowledged that ChatGPT significantly aids various aspects of their language learning process. This aligns with the views of Deng & Yu (2023), who state that chatbots fulfill three educational roles: acting as teaching assistants, learning partners, and personal tutors (Deng & Yu, 2023).

While the applications of ChatGPT are diverse, participants commonly utilize it to assist with assignments, enhance language learning, and support their final projects. Halaweh (2023) further supports this notion, asserting that ChatGPT can improve writing quality and serve as a valuable resource in higher education by generating text and summarizing information to save time.

From the interviews, it was revealed that participants employ ChatGPT as a reference tool and for developing writing ideas. They also use it to seek additional information related to their course materials. ChatGPT assists participants in comprehending assignment questions and finding specific answers, particularly when faced with challenging tasks. Moreover, it aids in understanding complex grammar and texts, as well as translating content. In the context of final projects, ChatGPT proves invaluable in providing ideas and writing references, enhancing participants' understanding of writing concepts.

The utilization of ChatGPT by participants in their language learning process aligns with Hong (2023), who asserts that ChatGPT can function as a personal language tutor by offering a wealth of resources and learning materials, explaining concepts, and providing detailed vocabulary usage examples, while also delivering prompt feedback on writing quality.

Participants believe that ChatGPT facilitates their self-directed learning. With the advantages provided by ChatGPT, it significantly supports their independent study efforts. This view is consistent with Xiao & Zhi (2023), who contend that chatbots can adapt to learners' proficiency levels and customize learning content through natural language processing (NLP) and machine learning techniques. Harry (2023) also mentioned that a significant benefit of using chatbots in education is their ability to provide tailored support to students. The findings from these interviews also resonate with the research conducted by Xiao & Zhi (2023), which discovered that ChatGPT can provide effective immediate feedback and personalized learning experiences.

5.3 Challenge in Using ChatGPT

In the utilization of ChatGPT, participants also encountered various challenges. Based on the interview findings, the most prevalent challenge reported by participants was the provision of information that may be inaccurate. Additionally, ChatGPT does not consistently grasp the context of the inquiries posed. These issues align with the observations of Gilson et al. (2023) and Shoufan (2023), who noted that ChatGPT does not

access up-to-date sources of information available on the internet due to its limited knowledge base, which is confined to the last update provided by OpenAI. Furthermore, Thirunavukarasu et al. (2023) stated that ChatGPT's capacity to deliver new information is not always reliable, and it can occasionally present inaccuracies alongside correct facts. Moreover, Kohnke et al. (2023) indicated that language learners may not recognize that ChatGPT is an AI system that is not culturally neutral and may inadvertently introduce bias, as its responses are primarily text-based rather than spoken.

According to the interview results, participants addressed these challenges by rephrasing their prompts to ChatGPT, thereby obtaining more accurate responses. Participants also indicated that to assess the accuracy of the information received from ChatGPT, they employed logic and personal knowledge, as well as comparing the information obtained from ChatGPT with reliable sources. Additionally, participants encountered challenges such as poor internet connectivity, frequent logouts from their ChatGPT accounts, and limitations on the word count for prompts or commands when interacting with ChatGPT. ChatGPT also provides quotation or journal references that often cannot be opened or found.

In addition to the challenges faced during usage, participants identified potential risks associated with ChatGPT that could threaten academic integrity. According to the interview data, participants expressed concerns that using ChatGPT to directly copy responses without paraphrasing could lead to plagiarism. This concern is consistent with the views of Xiao & Zhi, who stated that the outputs generated by ChatGPT are rephrased versions of its sources without appropriate citations, which may lead to issues such as plagiarism (Xiao & Zhi, 2023). Furthermore, the reliance on ChatGPT to complete assignments could pose a potential challenge to academic integrity. Participants noted that the ease of use of ChatGPT might facilitate academic dishonesty, particularly cheating. This perspective aligns with Ander (2023), who informed many professors and others in academia about ChatGPT, with most expressing immediate concerns that students might exploit it for cheating. They emphasized that any form of academic dishonesty, including misrepresenting another person's work as one's own, is prohibited and results in an unfair advantage for the perpetrator or an unfair disadvantage for other students.

6. Conclusion

The current study investigates the extent to which ChatGPT is utilized to assist language learners in their learning process. The findings indicate that participants have a comprehensive understanding of ChatGPT usage and can effectively employ prompts to interact with it. The use of ChatGPT in language learning by participants is generally to aid in completing assignments, facilitate language learning, and assist in completing their final projects. Participants also encountered several challenges when using ChatGPT. They often found that ChatGPT provided inaccurate information and lacked contextual understanding. Participants addressed these challenges by cross-referencing ChatGPT's answers or information with their personal knowledge and other reliable sources. Other challenges included issues with internet connectivity, word limit restrictions, ChatGPT's unnatural language, and frequent account logouts. The study also identified potential challenges related to the use of ChatGPT that could threaten academic integrity. Some of the challenges include the risk of plagiarism, using ChatGPT for cheating, and an over-reliance

on ChatGPT to complete assignments. The findings of this study on the use of ChatGPT in language learning underscore the need for ongoing research on the proper use of ChatGPT in the educational context. To address the research gap, future studies could employ experimental methods to obtain more comprehensive results regarding the use of ChatGPT to support language learning.

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